

The Thucydides Trap: Assessing the U.S.-China Rivalry and Its Implications for Global Stability

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Abstract

The Thucydides Trap, a concept coined by Harvard scholar Graham Allison, refers to the dangerous dynamic that arises when a rising power threatens to displace an established power, increasing the likelihood of conflict. This paper offers an in-depth analysis of the Thucydides Trap, its historical and theoretical background, and its implications for contemporary international relations, particularly between the United States and China. By examining the historical context of the Peloponnesian War, we explore the origins of the concept and its relevance in contemporary geopolitics. The paper also investigates the theories that underpin the Thucydides Trap, including realism, power transition theory, and the security dilemma. We then delve into case studies of past great power rivalries to draw lessons for the current U.S.-China relationship. The paper concludes with a discussion of potential strategies and policy recommendations to manage the tensions arising from the Thucydides Trap and minimize the risk of conflict. Through this comprehensive analysis, we aim to contribute to a better understanding of the Thucydides Trap and its implications for contemporary international politics.

Keywords: Thucydides Trap, Rising power, Established power, International relations, U.S.-China rivalry.

Introduction

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The Thucydides Trap, a concept coined by Harvard scholar Graham Allison², has become an increasingly popular framework for analyzing the growing rivalry between the United States and China. Drawing from the ancient historian Thucydides' account of the Peloponnesian War between Athens and Sparta³, the Thucydides Trap posits that when a rising power threatens to displace an established power, the risk of conflict is high. As China's economic, military, and political influence has grown, so too have concerns about the potential for a direct confrontation between the two superpowers.

This article aims to provide an in-depth examination of the Thucydides Trap in the context of the U.S.-China rivalry, exploring its historical and theoretical foundations, various dimensions of competition between the two powers, and the implications for global stability. Additionally, it will propose potential strategies for mitigating the risks of conflict, emphasizing the importance of confidence-building measures, cooperation, and strategic restraint in navigating the treacherous waters of great power competition.

The article is structured as follows: Section I will delve into the historical and theoretical background of the Thucydides Trap, examining its origins in Thucydides' account of the Peloponnesian War, as well as its relevance to contemporary international relations theory. Section II will explore the various dimensions of the U.S.-China rivalry, including economic, military, technological, and ideological competition. Section III will analyze the implications of this rivalry for global stability, focusing on the risks of conflict, the impact on international institutions and norms, and the effects on third parties and regional dynamics, and will outline potential strategies for mitigating the risks of the Thucydides Trap, emphasizing the importance of confidence-building measures, cooperation, and strategic restraint. Finally, Section IV will offer concluding remarks on the challenges and opportunities facing the U.S. and China as they navigate their evolving relationship.

I. Historical and theoretical background of the Thucydides Trap

² Graham Allison, *Destined for War: Can America and China Escape Thucydides' Trap?* Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, Boston, 2017, p. 6.

³ Thucydides, *The History of the Peloponnesian War*, translated by Rex Warner, Penguin Books, New York, 1954, pp. 22-23.

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A. Thucydides and the Peloponnesian War

The concept of the Thucydides Trap can be traced back to the ancient Greek historian Thucydides, who chronicled the Peloponnesian War (431-404 BCE) between Athens and Sparta. In his seminal work, *History of the Peloponnesian War*, Thucydides sought to identify the underlying causes of the conflict, arguing that it was the growth of Athenian power and the fear this engendered in Sparta that ultimately led to war⁴. This insight has been distilled by Allison into the notion of the Thucydides Trap, which posits that the rivalry between a rising power and an established power carries a significant risk of conflict⁵.

Thucydides' account of the Peloponnesian War offers a rich tapestry of events, personalities, and decision-making processes, providing valuable insights into the dynamics of great power competition and the factors that can contribute to the outbreak of conflict⁶. Among the key factors that Thucydides identified as contributing to the war were shifting alliances, strategic miscalculations, and the influence of domestic politics on foreign policy⁷. Moreover, Thucydides' analysis of the war's causes underscores the role of fear and insecurity in driving states to take aggressive actions, even when they may recognize the potential for disastrous consequences⁸.

B. The Thucydides Trap in contemporary international relations theory

The Thucydides Trap has gained considerable traction in contemporary international relations theory, particularly in discussions of the U.S.-China rivalry. The concept resonates with several prominent theoretical perspectives, including realism, liberal internationalism, and constructivism, each of which offers different insights into the dynamics of great power competition and the potential for conflict⁹.

Realism and the Thucydides Trap

⁴ Thucydides, *The History of the Peloponnesian War*, translated by Rex Warner, Penguin Books, New York, 1954, pp. 22-23.

⁵ Graham Allison, *Destined for War: Can America and China Escape Thucydides' Trap?* Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, Boston, 2017, p. 6.

⁶ Thucydides, *The History of the Peloponnesian War*, translated by Rex Warner, Penguin Books, New York, 1954, pp. 89-91.

⁷ Idib, pp. 112-114.

⁸ Idib, pp. 141-143.

⁹ Graham Allison, *Destined for War: Can America and China Escape Thucydides' Trap?* Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, Boston, 2017, pp. 13-15.

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Realism is perhaps the theoretical perspective most closely aligned with the Thucydides Trap, as it emphasizes the role of power and security in shaping state behavior¹⁰. Classical realist thinkers such as Thucydides and Hans Morgenthau argue that states are driven primarily by the desire for power and the need to ensure their security in an anarchic international system¹¹. According to this view, the competition between rising and established powers is an inherent feature of international politics, as states seek to maximize their power and protect their interests in the face of potential threats.

Structural realism, or neorealism, offers a more systematic account of the dynamics of great power competition¹². Proponents of this perspective, such as Kenneth Waltz and John Mearsheimer, contend that the structure of the international system, characterized by anarchy and the distribution of power, shapes state behavior and generates incentives for conflict¹³. For structural realists, the Thucydides Trap is a manifestation of the security dilemma, in which the efforts of states to enhance their security often provoke countermeasures by other states, leading to a spiral of tensions and the potential for conflict¹⁴.

Liberal internationalism and the Thucydides Trap

Liberal internationalism offers a somewhat unique perspective on the Thucydides Trap, focusing on the role of institutions, norms, and interdependence in shaping state behavior and the prospects for conflict¹⁵. While acknowledging the importance of power and security, liberal internationalists argue that states can also be motivated by the pursuit of cooperation and the desire to create a more peaceful and orderly international system¹⁶.

From a liberal internationalist perspective, the Thucydides Trap can be mitigated through the development of international institutions, the promotion of

¹⁰ Hans J. Morgenthau, *Politics Among Nations: The Struggle for Power and Peace*, Alfred A. Knopf, New York, 1948, p. 5.

¹¹ Idib, p. 8.

¹² Kenneth N. Waltz, *Theory of International Politics*, Addison-Wesley, Reading, MA, 1979, p. 97.

¹³ John J. Mearsheimer, *The Tragedy of Great Power Politics*, W.W. Norton & Company, New York, 2001, pp. 30-33.

¹⁴ Idib, pp. 39-42.

¹⁵ Robert O. Keohane and Joseph S. Nye, *Power and Interdependence*, 4th ed., Pearson, Boston, 2012, pp. 22-25.

¹⁶ Idib, pp. 29-31.

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democratic norms, and the deepening of economic interdependence between rival powers¹⁷. Proponents of this view, such as Robert Keohane and Joseph Nye, maintain that the liberal international order established after World War II has helped to prevent conflict among the great powers and foster a more stable global system¹⁸. However, critics argue that the liberal internationalist approach may be overly optimistic about the prospects for cooperation and the ability of institutions and norms to constrain state behavior, particularly in the face of rising nationalist sentiment and challenges to the liberal order¹⁹.

Constructivism and the Thucydides Trap

Constructivism offers a more nuanced account of the Thucydides Trap, emphasizing the role of ideas, beliefs, and identity in shaping state behavior and the dynamics of great power competition²⁰. Constructivists, such as Alexander Wendt and Martha Finnemore, argue that the interests and actions of states are not simply determined by material factors, but are also influenced by the social context and the shared understandings that constitute the international system²¹.

In the context of the Thucydides Trap, constructivists highlight the importance of perceptions, misperceptions, and the narratives that states construct about themselves and their rivals²². They argue that the risk of conflict can be exacerbated by factors such as national identity, historical grievances, and the framing of the rivalry in zero-sum terms²³. Similarly, constructivists contend that the potential for conflict can be mitigated by promoting shared values, fostering mutual understanding, and reframing the rivalry in more cooperative terms²⁴.

¹⁷ G. John Ikenberry, *Liberal Leviathan: The Origins, Crisis, and Transformation of the American World Order*, Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, 2011, pp. 45-48.

¹⁸ Robert O. Keohane and Joseph S. Nye, *Power and Interdependence*, 4th ed., Pearson, Boston, 2012, pp. 34-37.

¹⁹ G. John Ikenberry, *Liberal Leviathan: The Origins, Crisis, and Transformation of the American World Order*, Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, 2011, pp. 65-68.

²⁰ Alexander Wendt, *Social Theory of International Politics*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1999, pp. 18-21.

²¹ Martha Finnemore and Kathryn Sikkink, "Taking Stock: The Constructivist Research Program in International Relations and Comparative Politics", *Annual Review of Political Science*, 4, 2001, pp. 391-393.

²² Alexander Wendt, *Social Theory of International Politics*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1999, pp. 46-49.

²³ Idib, pp. 52-55.

²⁴ Martha Finnemore and Kathryn Sikkink, "Taking Stock: The Constructivist Research Program in International Relations and Comparative Politics", *Annual Review of Political Science*, 4, 2001, pp. 397-400.

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C. Critiques and limitations of the Thucydides Trap

Despite its popularity and theoretical resonance, the Thucydides Trap has also been subject to several critiques and limitations²⁵. Some critics argue that the concept is overly deterministic and simplistic, suggesting that the mere presence of a rising power does not inevitably lead to conflict with an established power²⁶. Indeed, historical cases such as the peaceful rise of the United States in the 19th century and the relatively peaceful emergence of post-war Germany and Japan as major economic powers suggest that the Thucydides Trap is not a universal law of international politics²⁷.

Others contend that the concept overlooks important domestic factors that can influence the behavior of states and the potential for conflict, such as regime type, domestic politics, and the role of leadership²⁸. For example, the Democratic Peace Theory posits that democracies are less likely to go to war with one another, suggesting that the risk of conflict between the U.S. and China may be mitigated by the diffusion of democratic norms and the strengthening of democratic institutions²⁹.

Furthermore, some critics argue that the Thucydides Trap is too focused on the material dimensions of power and neglects the role of non-material factors, such as soft power, diplomacy, and the influence of non-state actors³⁰. In an increasingly interconnected and complex world, the dynamics of great power competition are shaped not only by military and economic capabilities, but also by factors such as cultural appeal, the ability to shape global norms, and the projection of influence through transnational networks³¹.

Finally, some scholars question the empirical basis for the Thucydides Trap, pointing out that the concept relies heavily on a single historical case (the

²⁵ Barry Buzan and George Lawson, *The Global Transformation: History, Modernity, and the Making of International Relations*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2015, pp. 271-274.

²⁶ *Idib*, pp. 276-278.

²⁷ Fareed Zakaria, *The Post-American World*, W.W. Norton & Company, New York, 2008, pp. 104-107.

²⁸ James D. Fearon, "Domestic Political Audiences and the Escalation of International Disputes", *American Political Science Review*, 88:3, 1994, pp. 577-579.

²⁹ Bruce Russett and John R. Oneal, *Triangulating Peace: Democracy, Interdependence, and International Organizations*, W.W. Norton & Company, New York, 2001, pp. 23-26.

³⁰ Joseph S. Nye Jr., *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics*, Public Affairs, New York, 2004, pp. 16-19.

³¹ *Idib*, pp. 34-37.

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Peloponnesian War) and may not be generalizable to other contexts or time periods³². Moreover, they argue that the concept may be prone to confirmation bias, as it tends to focus on cases where conflict occurred and overlooks instances where rising powers and established powers were able to manage their rivalry peacefully³³.

Despite these critiques and limitations, the Thucydides Trap remains a useful analytical tool for understanding the dynamics of great power competition and the potential risks of conflict between the U.S. and China. By examining the historical and theoretical underpinnings of the concept, as well as the various dimensions of the rivalry and the implications for global stability, this article aims to provide a more nuanced and comprehensive assessment of the challenges and opportunities facing the two superpowers as they navigate their evolving relationship³⁴.

II. Assessing the U.S.-China Rivalry

A. Military Dimensions of the Rivalry

Military Capabilities and Modernization

The military dimension of the U.S.-China rivalry is perhaps the most visible and often-cited aspect of the competition between the two superpowers³⁵. The United States has long been the preeminent military power in the world, with unmatched global reach, technological superiority, and the ability to project power across multiple domains³⁶. However, China has been rapidly modernizing its military capabilities over the past few decades, investing heavily in areas such as missile technology, cyberwarfare, and anti-access/area denial (A2/AD) capabilities³⁷.

³² Barry Buzan and George Lawson, *The Global Transformation: History, Modernity, and the Making of International Relations*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2015, pp. 280-283.

³³ Idib, pp. 285-288.

³⁴ John J. Mearsheimer, *The Great Delusion: Liberal Dreams and International Realities*, Yale University Press, New Haven, 2018, pp. 245-249.

³⁵ Robert S. Ross, "The Problem with the Pivot: Obama's New Asia Policy Is Unnecessary and Counterproductive", *Foreign Affairs*, 91:6, 2012, pp. 70-72.

³⁶ Stephen G. Brooks and William C. Wohlforth, "The Rise and Fall of the Great Powers in the Twenty-first Century: China's Rise and the Fate of America's Global Position", *International Security*, 40:3, Winter 2015/16, pp. 12-15.

³⁷ Ronald O'Rourke, "China Naval Modernization: Implications for U.S. Navy Capabilities—Background and Issues for Congress", *Congressional Research Service*, updated July 17, 2020, pp. 3-6.

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As a result of these investments, China has made significant strides in closing the military gap with the United States, particularly in the Indo-Pacific region³⁸. According to a 2020 report by the U.S. Department of Defense, China now possesses the world's largest navy, with an overall battle force of approximately 350 ships and submarines, compared to the U.S. Navy's 293 ships³⁹. Moreover, China has developed a formidable array of ballistic and cruise missiles, capable of striking U.S. bases and assets in the region and complicating the U.S. military's ability to operate freely in the Western Pacific⁴⁰.

Force Posture and Regional Alliances

In addition to the military capabilities of the two superpowers, the U.S.-China rivalry is also shaped by their respective force posture and regional alliances⁴¹. The United States maintains a network of forward-deployed forces and bases in the Indo-Pacific region, including Japan, South Korea, Guam, and Australia, as well as a series of bilateral and multilateral defense agreements with regional partners⁴². These arrangements serve to reinforce U.S. presence and influence in the region and provide a bulwark against potential Chinese aggression.

China, on the other hand, has pursued a more assertive military posture in recent years, increasing its presence and activities in the South China Sea and establishing its first overseas military base in Djibouti⁴³. These moves have been seen by some analysts as evidence of China's growing ambition to challenge U.S. primacy in the region and expand its own sphere of influence⁴⁴. However, China's regional

³⁸ Andrew S. Erickson and Adam P. Liff, "China's Military Capabilities in the Post-Cold War Era: Implications for U.S. Strategy", in *Strategic Asia 2017-18: Power, Ideas, and Military Strategy in the Asia-Pacific*, edited by Ashley J. Tellis, Alison Szalwinski, and Michael Wills, National Bureau of Asian Research, Seattle, WA, 2017, pp. 54-58.

³⁹ U.S. Department of Defense, "Annual Report to Congress: Military and Security Developments Involving the People's Republic of China 2020", September 1, 2020, p. 89.

⁴⁰ Dennis M. Gormley, Andrew S. Erickson, and Jingdong Yuan, "A Potent Vector: Assessing Chinese Cruise Missile Developments", *Joint Force Quarterly*, 75 (4th Quarter 2014), p. 99.

⁴¹ Ely Ratner, "The Emergent Security Threats Reshaping China's Rise", *The Washington Quarterly*, 34:1, 2011, p. 29.

⁴² Michael J. Green and Zack Cooper, "Revitalizing the San Francisco System", in *Postwar Japan: Growth, Security, and Uncertainty since 1945*, edited by Michael J. Green and Zack Cooper, Georgetown University Press, Washington, D.C., 2017, pp. 109-111.

⁴³ Andrew S. Erickson and Joel Wuthnow, "Barriers, Springboards, and Benchmarks: China Conceptualizes the Pacific 'Island Chains'", *The China Quarterly*, 225 (March 2016), pp. 11-16.

⁴⁴ M. Taylor Fravel, "China's Strategy in the South China Sea," *Contemporary Southeast Asia*, 33:3, 2011, pp. 308-310.

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alliance network remains relatively limited, consisting primarily of its relationship with North Korea and a handful of other smaller partnerships⁴⁵.

Military Incidents and Near-Misses

The intensification of the U.S.-China military rivalry has led to several incidents and near-misses between their respective forces, raising concerns about the potential for miscalculation and escalation. These incidents have occurred in various domains, including air and naval encounters in the South China Sea and East China Sea, as well as incidents in the cyber domain and outer space⁴⁶.

For example, in 2001, a U.S. reconnaissance aircraft and a Chinese fighter jet collided near Hainan Island, resulting in the death of the Chinese pilot and the forced landing of the U.S. aircraft on Chinese territory. More recently, in 2018, a U.S. destroyer and a Chinese warship came within 45 yards of each other in the South China Sea, in what was described as an "unsafe and unprofessional" encounter⁴⁷.

B. Economic Dimensions of the Rivalry

Trade and Investment

The economic dimension of the U.S.-China rivalry is both a source of interdependence and competition between the two superpowers. The United States and China are each other's largest trading partners, with bilateral trade in goods and services amounting to over \$560 billion in 2019⁴⁸. However, this interdependence has also given rise to tensions and disputes over issues such as market access, intellectual property theft, and the role of state-owned enterprises.

The Trump administration's imposition of tariffs on Chinese imports in 2018 marked a significant escalation in the economic rivalry between the two countries, sparking a trade war that has had significant implications for both economies and the global trading system⁴⁹. While the Phase One trade deal signed in January 2020

⁴⁵ Peter Hays Gries, "The Koguryo Controversy, National Identity, and Sino-Korean Relations Today", *East Asia*, 22:4, 2005, pp. 3-4.

⁴⁶ Dean Cheng, "Chinese Views on Deterrence", *Joint Force Quarterly*, 60 (1st Quarter 2011), pp. 92-94.

⁴⁷ Robert D. Kaplan, "A New Cold War Has Begun", *Foreign Policy*, January/February 2019, p. 74.

⁴⁸ Richard E. Baldwin and Simon J. Evenett, "Value Creation and Trade in the 21st Century.", *Journal of International Business Studies*, 50:1, 2019, p. 2.

⁴⁹ Chad P. Bown and Eva Zhang, "Measuring Trump's 2018 Trade Protection: Five Takeaways", *Peterson Institute for International Economics*, Trade and Investment Policy Watch, February 15, p. 201

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provided some relief, the underlying issues driving the trade dispute remain largely unresolved.

In addition to trade, the U.S.-China rivalry also extends to the realm of investment, with both countries vying for influence and access to markets and resources around the world. Chinese foreign direct investment (FDI) in the United States has grown rapidly over the past decade, reaching a peak of \$46.5 billion in 2016 before declining in recent years due to increased scrutiny and regulatory barriers⁵⁰. Conversely, U.S. FDI in China has remained relatively stable, totaling approximately \$14 billion in 2019⁵¹.

Technology and Innovation

The competition between the U.S. and China extends to the realm of technology and innovation, with both countries seeking to gain an edge in key strategic sectors such as artificial intelligence, quantum computing, biotechnology, and advanced manufacturing⁵². This technological rivalry has implications not only for economic growth and competitiveness but also for national security, as technological dominance in these areas could confer significant military and intelligence advantages⁵³.

One of the most prominent manifestations of this rivalry has been the battle over 5G telecommunications technology, with the U.S. government taking a series of measures to restrict Chinese telecom giant Huawei's access to the U.S. market and urging allies to do the same⁵⁴. These efforts have been driven by concerns about the potential security risks posed by Chinese-built 5G networks, as well as the desire to maintain U.S. technological leadership in this critical domain⁵⁵.

⁵⁰ Daniel H. Rosen and Thilo Hanemann, "An American Open Door? Maximizing the Benefits of Chinese Foreign Direct Investment", *Asia Society Special Report*, May 2011, p. 1.

⁵¹ Derek Scissors, "China Global Investment Tracker," *American Enterprise Institute*, 2021, p. 11.

⁵² Richard P. Suttmeier and Xiangkui Yao, "China's Post-WTO Technology Policy: Standards, Software, and the Changing Nature of Techno-Nationalism," National Bureau of Asian Research, Special Report 7 (May 2004), pp. 5-31.

⁵³ Elsa B. Kania, "Battlefield Singularity: Artificial Intelligence, Military Revolution, and China's Future Military Power," *Center for a New American Security*, November 28, 2017, pp. 16-26.

⁵⁴ Paul Triolo, Kevin Allison, and Dr. Alexis Crow, "The Geopolitics of 5G", *Eurasia Group, White Paper*, November 15, 2018, pp. 10-11.

⁵⁵ Danielle Cave, Tom Uren, and Daria Impiombato, "Huawei and Australia's 5G Network", *Australian Strategic Policy Institute*, Issue Brief, Report No. 19, 2018, pp. 9-10.

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In addition to 5G, the U.S. and China are also engaged in a fierce competition in artificial intelligence (AI). Both countries have unveiled national AI strategies and invested heavily in AI research and development, with China aiming to become the world leader in AI by 2030⁵⁶. While the U.S. currently leads in AI research and innovation, China's vast data resources, growing talent pool, and government support for AI development pose a significant challenge to U.S. dominance in this critical technology sector⁵⁷.

Economic Statecraft and Geoeconomics

The economic dimensions of the U.S.-China rivalry are not limited to trade, investment, and technology but also encompass the broader realm of economic statecraft and geoeconomics. Both the U.S. and China have sought to leverage their economic power to advance their strategic objectives and shape the global economic landscape in ways that serve their interests.

One of the key instruments of China's economic statecraft has been the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), a massive infrastructure investment and development program aimed at connecting China to markets and resources across Asia, Europe, and Africa⁵⁸. Launched in 2013, the BRI has become a central pillar of China's foreign policy and a powerful tool for expanding its economic and political influence around the world.

The United States, for its part, has employed a range of economic statecraft tools, including sanctions, export controls, and investment screening mechanisms, to counter perceived threats and advance its strategic interests. For example, the Trump administration's use of tariffs as a tool of economic coercion against China and other trading partners has been widely seen as a departure from traditional U.S. support for free trade and multilateralism⁵⁹.

⁵⁶ Kai-Fu Lee, *AI Superpowers: China, Silicon Valley, and the New World Order*, Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, Boston, 2018, pp. 10-20.

⁵⁷ Jeffrey Ding, *Deciphering China's AI Dream*, Future of Humanity Institute, University of Oxford, Technical Report, March 2018, pp. 1-10.

⁵⁸ Nadège Rolland, "China's Eurasian Century? Political and Strategic Implications of the Belt and Road Initiative," *National Bureau of Asian Research*, May 10, 2017, pp. 24-30.

⁵⁹ Chad P. Bown, "The 2018 Trade War and the End of Dispute Settlement as We Knew It", *Journal of International Economic Law*, 22:4, 2019, pp. 585-588.

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In addition, the U.S. has pursued a series of economic initiatives aimed at countering China's growing influence, such as the Blue Dot Network, an infrastructure development framework designed to promote high-quality, sustainable infrastructure investments in the Indo-Pacific region⁶⁰. Q⁶¹.

C. Diplomatic and Ideological Dimensions of the Rivalry

Competing Visions for the International Order

The diplomatic and ideological dimensions of the U.S.-China rivalry are rooted in the competing visions of the two superpowers for the international order and the norms and institutions that underpin it. The United States, as the architect and primary guarantor of the liberal international order, has long championed principles such as democracy, human rights, and free markets, as well as the rules-based multilateral institutions that embody these values⁶². China, by contrast, has put forward a vision of a more multipolar and less ideologically driven international order, in which the principle of non-interference in the internal affairs of other states is paramount. This vision is often associated with the concept of a "community of shared future for mankind," which Chinese leaders have frequently invoked in their public statements and diplomatic initiatives⁶³.

Diplomatic Competition and Influence-Building

The U.S.-China rivalry also plays out in the diplomatic sphere, with both countries vying for influence and support among other nations and within international institutions. This competition has manifested itself in many ways, including diplomatic initiatives, foreign aid, and public diplomacy efforts aimed at shaping global narratives and perceptions⁶⁴.

China's growing diplomatic influence has been evident in its expanding diplomatic presence around the world, as well as its increasing influence within

⁶⁰ Jonathan E. Hillman, "The Blue Dot Network: The United States' Answer to China's Belt and Road?" Center for Strategic and International Studies, November 15, 2019, pp. 1-5.

⁶¹ Henry Farrell and Abraham L. Newman, "Weaponized Interdependence: How Global Economic Networks Shape State Coercion", *International Security*, 44:1, 2019, pp. 53-56.

⁶² G. John Ikenberry, *Liberal Leviathan: The Origins, Crisis, and Transformation of the American World Order*, Princeton University Press, 2011, p. 15.

⁶³ Jinping Xi, "Speech at the United Nations Office at Geneva", United Nations Office at Geneva, Switzerland, January 18, 2017.

⁶⁴ David Shambaugh, *China Goes Global: The Partial Power*, Oxford University Press, 2013, pp. 93-95.

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international institutions such as the United Nations (UN), World Bank, and World Trade Organization (WTO)⁶⁵. In recent years, China has successfully secured leadership positions in several key UN agencies, including the International Civil Aviation Organization and the International Telecommunication Union, raising concerns among some U.S. policymakers and analysts about the potential erosion of U.S. influence in these organizations⁶⁶.

The United States, for its part, has sought to counter China's growing diplomatic influence through a variety of means, including strengthening its traditional alliances and partnerships, building new coalitions and networks, and leveraging its soft power resources to promote its values and interests⁶⁷. However, these efforts have faced challenges in recent years due to perceived U.S. disengagement from multilateral institutions and a decline in global perceptions of U.S. leadership⁶⁸.

Ideological Competition and the Battle for Hearts and Minds

The ideological dimension of the U.S.-China rivalry is perhaps the least tangible but arguably one of the most consequential aspects of the competition. At its core, this struggle is about the battle for hearts and minds, both within and outside the borders of the two superpowers⁶⁹.

In the United States, there has been growing concern about the influence of the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) and its efforts to shape global narratives and public opinion through a variety of means, including state-sponsored media outlets, Confucius Institutes, and other forms of cultural and educational exchange. These concerns have led to a series of policy responses, such as the tightening of restrictions on Chinese state media operating in the U.S. and the closure of some Confucius Institutes⁷⁰.

⁶⁵ Elizabeth C. Economy and Michael Levi, *Necessary: How China's Resource Quest is Changing the World*, Oxford University Press, 2014, pp. 50-51.

⁶⁶ Colum Lynch III, "China's Long Arm Reaches Into American Campuses," *Foreign Policy*, March 7, 2018, pp. 3-9.

⁶⁷ Joseph S. Nye Jr., *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics*, Public Affairs, 2004, pp. 90-91.

⁶⁸ Pew Research Center, "U.S. Image Plummets Internationally as Most Say Country Has Managed Coronavirus Badly," Pew Research Center, September 15, 2020, pp. 6-7.

⁶⁹ Joseph S. Nye Jr., *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics*, Public Affairs, 2004, p. 95.

⁷⁰ U.S. Department of State, "Designation of Additional Chinese Media Entities as Foreign Missions," Press Statement, June 22, 2020.

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China, for its part, has been engaged in a concerted effort to promote its own narrative and model of development, both domestically and internationally. This effort has been driven by a belief among Chinese leaders that the "China model" – characterized by strong state control over the economy, political stability, and rapid development – offers a viable alternative to the liberal democratic model championed by the United States and other Western countries⁷¹.

The ideological competition between the U.S. and China is not limited to the realm of soft power and public diplomacy but also extends to the domestic political sphere in both countries. In the United States, concerns about China's influence and intentions have contributed to a growing bipartisan consensus on the need to adopt a more confrontational approach toward China⁷².

III. Implications for Global Stability

A. Military Escalation and the Risk of Conflict

Flashpoints and Crisis Scenarios

One of the most pressing concerns arising from the U.S.-China rivalry is the potential for military escalation and conflict, either because of deliberate actions by one or both parties or through miscalculation and miscommunication. Several flashpoints and crisis scenarios have been identified as potential triggers for conflict, including tensions in the South China Sea, the East China Sea, and the Taiwan Strait, as well as broader concerns about military competition in areas such as outer space and cyberspace⁷³.

The South China Sea has emerged as a particularly contentious issue in the U.S.-China rivalry, with China's extensive land reclamation and militarization activities in the region raising concerns among the U.S. and its allies about the potential for conflict and the erosion of the rules-based international order. In response, the U.S.

⁷¹ Weiwei Zhang, *The China Wave : Rise of a Civilizational State*, World Century Publishing Corporation, Hackensack, 2012, pp. 12-13.

⁷² Robert Sutter, *U.S.-Chinese Relations: Perilous Past, Pragmatic Present*, Rowman & Littlefield, Washington, D.C., 2010, p. 220.

⁷³ Ely Ratner, "Rising to the China Challenge: Renewing American Competitiveness in the Indo-Pacific," Center for a New American Security, December 2019, p. 18.

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has stepped up its freedom of navigation operations and military exercises in the area, leading to a series of tense encounters between U.S. and Chinese forces⁷⁴.

The Taiwan Strait is another potential flashpoint, with the U.S. commitment to Taiwan's security and defense serving as a longstanding source of tension in U.S.-China relations⁷⁵. Recent years have seen an increase in Chinese military activity around Taiwan, including regular air and naval patrols and large-scale military exercises simulating an invasion of the island. These actions have prompted the U.S. to increase its support for Taiwan, including through arms sales and high-level diplomatic engagements, heightening the risk of a potential military confrontation.

Escalation Dynamics and the Role of Third Parties

The potential for conflict between the U.S. and China is not only a function of their bilateral interactions but also depends on the actions of third parties, including regional states and non-state actors. The involvement of third parties in potential crisis scenarios can complicate the dynamics of escalation and make it more difficult for the U.S. and China to manage tensions and avoid conflict⁷⁶.

For example, the South China Sea dispute involves multiple claimants, including several U.S. allies and partners such as the Philippines and Vietnam, which have their own interests and objectives in the region⁷⁷. The presence of these actors increases the potential for incidents and conflicts that could inadvertently draw the U.S. and China into a larger confrontation. Similarly, in the Taiwan Strait, the actions of the Taiwanese government and military, as well as other regional actors such as Japan, could influence the dynamics of a potential crisis and the likelihood of conflict between the U.S. and China⁷⁸.

Mitigating the Risk of Conflict

⁷⁴ Ronald O'Rourke, "U.S.-China Strategic Competition in South and East China Seas", Congressional Research Service, August 15, 2019, p. 3.

⁷⁵ Thomas J. Christensen, "China, the U.S.-Japan Alliance, and the Security Dilemma in East Asia", *International Security*, 23:4, 1999, pp. 55-56.

⁷⁶ M. Taylor Fravel, "China's Strategy in the South China Sea", *Contemporary Southeast Asia*, 33:3, 2011, pp. 305-306.

⁷⁷ Leszek Buszynski, "The South China Sea: Oil, Maritime Claims, and U.S.-China Strategic Rivalry", *The Washington Quarterly*, 35:2, 2012, pp. 139-140.

⁷⁸ Bonnie S. Glaser, and Brittany Billingsley, "Taiwan's Role in the East China Sea Peace Initiative", Center for Strategic and International Studies, April 12, 2013, pp. 7-8.

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Given the significant risks associated with military escalation and conflict between the U.S. and China, efforts to mitigate these risks and manage the rivalry in a stable and peaceful manner are of paramount importance. Several measures have been proposed to this end, including confidence-building measures, crisis management mechanisms, and arms control agreements.

Confidence-building measures (CBMs) are designed to reduce mistrust and misperceptions between the U.S. and China by enhancing transparency and communication about military activities and intentions. Examples of CBMs include the establishment of military hotlines, mutual notification of military exercises, and the exchange of military personnel for training and education purposes⁷⁹. While some CBMs have been implemented in the U.S.-China relationship, their effectiveness has been limited by mutual suspicion and concerns about revealing sensitive information⁸⁰.

Crisis management mechanisms, on the other hand, focus on reducing the risk of escalation and unintended conflict during periods of heightened tension or crises. These mechanisms can take various forms, including joint crisis management centers, pre-established crisis communication protocols, and regular consultations between military and civilian officials. The U.S. and China have established some crisis management mechanisms, such as the Military Maritime Consultative Agreement and the 2014 memorandum of understanding on air and maritime encounters⁸¹. However, there is room for further development and improvement of these mechanisms to ensure their effectiveness in managing potential crises.

Arms control agreements can also play a role in managing the U.S.-China rivalry by limiting the development and deployment of destabilizing weapons systems and reducing the incentives for arms racing. While the U.S. and China have not yet entered into any formal arms control agreements, they have participated in multilateral arms control and nonproliferation regimes, such as the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty and the Missile Technology Control Regime. There have been calls for the U.S.

⁷⁹ Michael E. O'Hanlon, "China's Challenge to Pax Americana: U.S. Military Options in Asia", *The Washington Quarterly*, 38:3, 2015, pp. 172-173.

⁸⁰ Michael D. Swaine, and M. Taylor Fravel, "China's Assertive Behavior: Part One: On 'Core Interests'", *China Leadership Monitor*, 34, 2011, p. 7.

⁸¹ U.S. Department of Defense, "Memorandum of Understanding On the Rules of Behavior for Safety of Air and Maritime Encounters Between the Department of Defense of the United States of America And the Ministry of National Defense of the People's Republic of China", November 9, 2014.

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and China to engage in bilateral arms control negotiations, particularly in areas such as outer space and cyberspace, where the potential for destabilizing arms races is high⁸².

B. Economic Competition and the Impact on Global Growth

Decoupling and its Consequences

The intensifying rivalry between the U.S. and China has raised concerns about the potential for a process of economic decoupling, whereby the two countries disentangle their deeply integrated economies and pursue separate development paths. Decoupling could take several forms, including the restriction of trade and investment flows, the imposition of technology controls, and the creation of competing economic blocs⁸³. Proponents of decoupling argue that it is necessary to protect national security and prevent the flow of critical technologies and resources to China⁸⁴. However, critics warn that decoupling could have significant negative consequences for both the U.S. and China, as well as the global economy more broadly. These consequences include reduced economic growth, increased costs for consumers and businesses, and the fragmentation of global supply chains⁸⁵.

Economic Statecraft and the Weaponization of Interdependence

The U.S.-China rivalry has also seen the increased use of economic statecraft as a tool of competition and coercion. Economic statecraft refers to the use of economic instruments, such as trade, investment, and financial measures, to advance strategic objectives and influence the behavior of other states⁸⁶. In the context of the U.S.-China rivalry, economic statecraft has taken on a more aggressive and coercive character, with both countries using their economic power to punish adversaries and reward allies. The U.S., for example, has employed a range of economic measures

⁸² Michael Krepon, and Christopher Clary, *Space Assurance or Space Dominance? The Case Against Weaponizing Space*, Henry L. Stimson Center, Washington, D.C., 2003, pp. 12-13.

⁸³ Graham Allison, *Destined for War: Can America and China Escape Thucydides' Trap?* Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, Boston, 2017, p. 202.

⁸⁴ Joseph S. Nye Jr., *The Future of Power*, Public Affairs, New York, 2011, p. 88.

⁸⁵ Aaron L. Friedberg, "Competing with China," *Survival*, 60:3, 2018, pp. 7-64, p. 22.

⁸⁶ Edward N. Luttwak, *The Rise of China vs. the Logic of Strategy*, Belknap Press, Cambridge, 2012, p. 47.

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against China, including tariffs, export controls, and sanctions, as part of its broader effort to counter China's rise and promote its own economic interests⁸⁷. China, in turn, has made use of its economic leverage to punish countries that challenge its interests or support U.S. policies, such as by imposing economic sanctions, restricting access to its markets, and withholding investment and infrastructure financing.

The weaponization of interdependence – the use of economic interdependence as a source of power and leverage – represents a significant departure from the liberal economic order that has underpinned the global economy for much of the post-World War II period. It raises questions about the sustainability of this order and the potential for a more fragmented and conflict-prone global economic system⁸⁸.

The U.S.-China rivalry also has implications for global economic governance, including the functioning of international economic institutions and the development of global economic rules and norms. As the world's two largest economies, the U.S. and China play a critical role in shaping the global economic agenda and determining the future direction of the international economic system⁸⁹.

However, the intensifying rivalry between the U.S. and China has made it more difficult for them to cooperate on global economic issues, resulting in a growing fragmentation and dysfunction in the international economic order⁹⁰. This can be seen, for example, in the ongoing disputes over trade and technology policy, which have led to a stalemate in the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the emergence of competing regional trade agreements. Additionally, the U.S.-China rivalry has raised concerns about the potential for a "race to the bottom" in areas such as environmental, labor, and regulatory standards, as each country seeks to gain a competitive advantage by undercutting the other⁹¹. This could undermine global efforts to address pressing challenges such as climate change, income inequality, and financial stability.

⁸⁷ Joseph S. Nye Jr., "The Kindleberger Trap," *Project Syndicate*, January 9, 2017, p. 3.

⁸⁸ Graham Allison, *Destined for War*, p. 255.

⁸⁹ Joseph S. Nye Jr., *The Future of Power*, p. 117.

⁹⁰ Aaron L. Friedberg, "Competing with China," p. 35.

⁹¹ Dani Rodrik, "Globalization, Structural Change and Productivity Growth", NBER Working Paper No. 17143, 2011, p. 42.

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C. The Geopolitical Dimension: Shifting Alliances and the Risk of Proliferation

Shifting Alliances and the Emergence of New Blocs

The U.S.-China rivalry has led to a realignment of global power relations, with countries increasingly being forced to choose sides or navigate a delicate balancing act between the two superpowers⁹². This has given rise to new alliances and partnerships, as well as the reconfiguration of existing ones, as countries seek to advance their interests and hedge against the uncertainties of the changing geopolitical landscape⁹³.

In the Asia-Pacific region, for example, the U.S. has sought to strengthen its alliances with Japan, Australia, and South Korea, as well as forge new partnerships with countries such as India and Vietnam, to counter China's growing influence⁹⁴. China, meanwhile, has pursued a more assertive foreign policy, using its economic power to cultivate relationships with countries in the region and beyond, including through initiatives such as the Belt and Road Initiative and the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank⁹⁵.

The emergence of new blocs and the reconfiguration of existing alliances raise concerns about the potential for a more polarized and conflict-prone international system⁹⁶. This could undermine the stability and predictability that have characterized the post-Cold War era and increase the risk of crises and conflicts among the major powers⁹⁷.

The U.S.-China rivalry also has implications for global nonproliferation efforts, particularly with respect to the spread of nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction (WMDs). The intensifying competition between the U.S. and China could encourage other states to pursue their own nuclear capabilities, either as

⁹² Ely Ratner, "Rising to the China Challenge: Renewing American Competitiveness in the Indo-Pacific", *Center for a New American Security*, Dec. 2019, p. 12.

⁹³ Evelyn Goh, *The Struggle for Order: Hegemony, Hierarchy, and Transition in Post-Cold War East Asia*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2013, p. 79.

⁹⁴ Evan S. Medeiros, "The Changing Fundamentals of US-China Relations," *The Washington Quarterly*, 41:3, 2018, pp. 93-119, p. 104.

⁹⁵ Jean-Marc F. Blanchard, and Norrin M. Ripsman, *Economic Statecraft and Foreign Policy: Sanctions, Incentives, and Target State Calculations*, Routledge, New York, 2013, p. 138.

⁹⁶ Stephen M. Walt, "Alliances in a Unipolar World", *World Politics*, 61:1, 2009, p. 95.

⁹⁷ Christopher Layne, "The Great Power Rivalry and the Coming War with China", p. 460.

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a means of enhancing their security or as a bargaining chip in their relations with the major powers⁹⁸.

To address possible risks, it is important for the U.S. and China to work together to strengthen the international nonproliferation regime and reaffirm their commitment to nonproliferation norms⁹⁹. This could involve taking concrete steps to reduce their own nuclear arsenals and promote disarmament, as well as cooperating on initiatives aimed at preventing the spread of nuclear weapons and other WMDs to non-state actors and countries of concern¹⁰⁰. Additionally, the U.S. and China could work together to strengthen the enforcement mechanisms of existing nonproliferation regimes and develop new norms and agreements to address emerging proliferation challenges, such as the potential militarization of outer space and the proliferation of advanced conventional weapons¹⁰¹.

IV. Conclusion

The Thucydides Trap, as a theoretical framework for understanding the U.S.-China rivalry, offers important insights into the dynamics and risks associated with the rise of a new great power challenging an established one. While the historical record suggests that the odds of conflict between the U.S. and China are high, it is important to recognize that history is not destiny, and that the actions and choices of leaders on both sides will play a critical role in determining the outcome of the rivalry¹⁰².

The U.S. and China face a complex array of challenges as they navigate their rivalry, including the potential for military escalation and conflict, the impact of economic competition on global growth and stability, and the geopolitical implications of shifting alliances and the erosion of nonproliferation norms¹⁰³. To manage these risks and avoid the worst-case scenarios associated with the Thucydides Trap, it is

⁹⁸ Matthew Kroenig, and Tristan Volpe, "3D Printing the Bomb? The Nuclear Nonproliferation Challenge," *The Washington Quarterly*, 38:3, 2015, pp. 7-19, p. 11.

⁹⁹ George Perkovich, and James M. Acton, "Establishing Political Conditions to Enhance the Feasibility of Abolishing Nuclear Weapons", *The Adelphi Papers*, 48:396, p. 29.

¹⁰⁰ Mark Fitzpatrick, *Asia's Latent Nuclear Powers: Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan*, International Institute for Strategic Studies, London, 2016, p. 75.

¹⁰¹ John J. Mearsheimer, *The Tragedy of Great Power Politics*, W.W. Norton & Company, New York, 2014, p. 371.

¹⁰² Graham Allison, *Destined for War: Can America and China Escape Thucydides' Trap?* Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, Boston, 2017, p. 305.

¹⁰³ Aaron L. Friedberg, "Competing with China", *Survival*, 60:3, 2018, p. 50.

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essential for the U.S. and China to find ways to cooperate on issues of common interest and develop mechanisms for managing their differences in a stable and peaceful manner¹⁰⁴.

At the same time, it is important for the international community to recognize that the U.S.-China rivalry is not solely a bilateral issue, but one that has profound implications for global peace and prosperity¹⁰⁵. As such, it is incumbent upon all states to play a constructive role in managing the rivalry and promoting a rules-based international order that can accommodate the interests and aspirations of both the U.S. and China, as well as other emerging powers¹⁰⁶. By doing so, it may be possible to escape the Thucydides Trap and chart a course towards a more stable and cooperative international system¹⁰⁷.

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"The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest" ("Crossmark")

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¹⁰⁵ Joseph S. Nye Jr., "The Kindleberger Trap", *Project Syndicate*, 9 Jan. 2017, p. 7.

¹⁰⁶ Andrew Hurrell, *On Global Order: Power, Values, and the Constitution of International Society*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2007, p. 289.

¹⁰⁷ Charles A. Kupchan, and Peter L. Trubowitz, "Dead Center: The Demise of Liberal Internationalism in the United States", *International Security*, 32:2, 2007, p. 40.

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